

MPowerBIO

eM-POWERing SME Clusters to help SMEs to overcome the valley of death

D6.3 Leaflet and corporate image

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Partners

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Bio-based Industries Consortium

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2	TechTour Global https://www.techtour.com/	TTG	BG	SME
3	CLIB https://www.clib2021.de/	CLIB	DE	Non-profit SME/Cluster
4	Corporacion Tecnologica de Andalucia https://www.corporaciontecnologica.com/es/	CTA	ES	Non-profit Research Centre/Cluster
5	Italbiotec https://www.italbiotec.it/	IBT	IT	Non-profit Research Centre/Cluster
6	FoodScale Hub https://foodscaleshub.com/	FSH	RS	Non-profit Association /Cluster
7	EIT Food https://www.eitfood.eu/	EIT	BE	Non-profit Association
8	Irish Bioeconomy Foundation https://bioeconomyfoundation.com/	IBF	IE	Non-profit SME/Cluster
9	Q-Plan International https://qplan-intl.gr/	QPL	GR	SME
10	Sustainable Innovations Europe https://www.sustainableinnovations.eu/	SIE	ES	SME

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1. Deliverable Description

Deliverable 6.3 consists of two main elements; a leaflet and corporate image.

To give the project a unique corporate image a design manual has been developed in the beginning of the project and was finalised in M3. The design manual outlines the fundamentals of the project's design principles and includes:

- The MPowerBIO logo
- Graphic icon
- Fonts
- Colors
- PowerPoint template
- Roll-up template
- Word document
- Infographic

Figure 1 Design manual

Figure 2 Logo and graphic icon

Figure 3 Fonts and colors

Figure 4 PowerPoint

Figure 5 Roll-ups

Figure 6 Word document

Figure 7 Infographic

Based on the corporate image described in the design manual a leaflet has been developed, which summarises the project and its' objectives, expected results, the consortium and contacts. The leaflet was finalised according to plan in M6.

Figure 8 Leaflet page 1+4

Figure 9 Leaflet page 2+3

In addition to the leaflet and the corporate image several templates have been developed, which can be used for training materials. These include a PowerPoint and a Word template as well as two different roll-ups.

2. How the deliverable relates to the objectives of WP6

The leaflet is one part of the multi-step and multi-channel approach designed to reach and engage stakeholders and is a mean to provide targeted information to SMEs about the project and the benefits of participating in the programme. The leaflet is thereby supporting the objective of raising awareness about the project to the SMEs.